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**Sintering of a fine-grained BaCeO₃ powder obtained from a
co-precipitation method**

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Abstract. The formation of BaCeO₃ by a co-precipitation method is described herein. The co-precipitation route leads to an orange (BaCe)-precursor powder (**1**). To improve the sintering behaviour, a small amount of Ge⁴⁺ was incorporated, leading to a (BaCe_{0.95}/Ge_{0.05})-precursor (**2**). Both precursor powders results in fine-grained preceramic powders (**1A**, **2A**) after calcination. The shrinkage and sintering behaviour of resulting powder compacts were studied in comparison to a coarse-grained mixed-oxide BaCeO₃ powder (**3**). Compacts of **2A** reach a relative density of 90 % after sintering at 1350 °C with grain-sizes between 0.9–3.2 μm. On the other hand ceramics of **1A** and **3** have, after sintering at 1500 °C (10 h), relative densities of 85 % and 76 %, respectively. Ceramic bodies of **1A** consisted of phase-pure orthorhombic BaCeO₃, whereas bodies of **2A** show reflections of BaCeO₃ and a Ba₂GeO₄ phase. DTA investigations of samples **1A** and **2A** reveal three phase transitions at 255 °C (**1A**) and 256 °C

(2A) as well as 383 °C (1A) and 380 °C (2A). A very weak one can be obtained in the range 880–910 °C.

Keywords: *barium cerate; barium orthogermanate; precursor; differential thermoanalytic; ceramic; sintering*

Introduction

Perovskite materials based on BaCeO₃ have high proton conductivity in hydrogen and water containing atmospheres between 600–800 °C. Therefore, BaCeO₃ based compounds are candidates to replace yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) electrolyte materials for solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9]. Benlhachemi et al. [10] and Popescu et al. [11] reported on the catalytic oxidation of methane in the presence of BaCeO₃. Furthermore, barium cerate can be also applied as a functional material for semiconductor gas sensors [12] and solid solution of the type BaTi_{1-x}Ce_xO₃ can be used for capacitor applications [13,14,15,16,17,18]. High-resolution neutron diffraction measurements up to 1000 °C by Knight [19,20] and Genet et al. [21] evidence three phase transitions of BaCeO₃. A first transition at 290 °C leads from a primitive orthorhombic perovskite structure (Spacegroup: Pmcn) to the body-centred one (Incn), a second at 400 °C to a rhombohedrally distorted one ($F\bar{3}2$) and the last transition at 900 °C to the cubic perovskite structure ($Pm\bar{3}m$).

Compacts on the basis of BaCeO₃ generally reveal only a moderate densification behaviour. For application such as capacitors or in SOFCs the density of the sintering bodies must be high [22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30]. On the other hand, sintering temperatures above 1500 °C should be avoided because BaCeO₃ melts incongruently at 1480 °C ± 5 °C with the formation of CeO₂ and a liquid containing BaO [6,31]. The densification behaviour can be improved and thus the sintering temperature reduced by using fine-grained powders and sintering additives [32,33,34]. Apart from the mixed-oxide method, which results in coarse-grained powders,

some wet chemical syntheses have been developed to obtain fine-grained BaCeO₃ powders such as various precursor complex methods, solvothermal- and sol-gel syntheses [35,36,37,38,39,40,41]. Pechini based routes are reported by Lee et al. [42] and Su et al. [43]. Almost all of those preparation methods use as starting materials Ce³⁺ compounds to obtain BaCeO₃. On the other hand, it seems to be advantageous to use Ce⁴⁺ compounds as starting material to synthesize BaTi_{1-x}Ce_xO₃ solid solutions by wet chemical methods [44]. In this paper we therefore describe a simple co-precipitation method starting from a Ce⁴⁺ compound to obtain fine-grained BaCeO₃. Additionally, we have studied the phase evolution during the decomposition process. The sintering behaviour of BaCeO₃ compacts, the microstructure of the resulting ceramic bodies, and the influence of a sintering additive have been also investigated. Phase transition temperatures have been determined by DTA measurements.

2. Experimental

2.1. Material preparation

Ba(NO₃)₂ (0.04 mol, *Merck*) and (NH₄)₂Ce(NO₃)₆ (0.04 mol, *Alfa Aesar*) were separately dissolved in 50 ml water. Both solutions were combined in a round bottom flask cooled with ice. Under vigorous stirring ammonium oxalate solution (0.16 mol in 440 ml water) and afterwards a cooled mixture (5 °C) of 66 ml concentrated ammonia solution (25%), 33 ml hydrogen peroxide solution (30%) and 50 ml water were added starting an exothermic reaction to form an orange precipitate. The mixture was stirred in an ice bath for 30 minutes, filtered and the precipitate was washed with water several times. The resulting orange product (**1**) was dried in air for 1 day and then dried over H₂SO₄ in a desiccator for 7 days.

Precursor **2** was synthesized analogously to precursor **1**. However 5 mol% of (NH₄)₂Ce(NO₃)₆ was substituted by Ge(OC₂H₅)₄.

For the shrinkage and sintering studies the precursors **1** and **2** were calcined in static air at 980 °C by a heating rate controlled thermal treatment to obtain fine-grained powders **1A** and **2A**, as described below. These calcined powders were milled with ZrO₂-balls in propan-2-ol for 2 h ($m_{\text{powder}}:m_{\text{balls}} = 1:4$). After filtering and drying, the powders were mixed with 5 mass% of a saturated aqueous solution of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as a pressing aid, then the powders were pressed to discs with a green density of about 2.7–2.8 g/cm³.

For comparative purposes, BaCeO₃ powder (**3**) was also prepared via a conventional mixed-oxide method. Equivalent amounts of BaCO₃ (*J.T. Baker Inc*) and CeO₂ (*Acros Organics*) were milled for 24 h using ZrO₂-balls in water ($m_{\text{powder}}:m_{\text{balls}}:m_{\text{water}} = 1:1:4$). After filtering off and drying the mixture was calcined in static air (rate 10 K/min) for 4 h at 1150 °C. The remaining steps were identical to those mentioned above (as for **1A**). However, the green densities of the compacts were 3.5 g/cm³.

2.2. Characterization

X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded on a *STOE STADI MP* diffractometer at 25 °C using Co-K α_1 radiation. The powder patterns were indexed and refined with the software suite WinXPOW [45] using the TREOR method [46]. Fourier transform attenuated total reflection infrared (ATR-IR) spectra in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ (resolution: 4 cm⁻¹) were obtained using a Tensor 27 FT-IR spectrometer from *Bruker* with an ATR unit (MVP 2 Series from *Harrick*). Dilatometric (shrinkage) investigations were performed in a flowing synthetic air atmosphere (50 ml/min) in a TMA 92-16.18 unit from *Setaram*. Thermogravimetric (TG) and differential thermoanalytic (DTA) measurements were achieved using a *Netzsch* STA 449 System (heating-/cooling rate 10 K/min, flowing air or argon (30 ml/min)). For the investigation of phase transitions each DTA sample was measured three times to ensure reproducibility. The specific surface area was determined using nitrogen three-point BET (Nova 1000, *Quantachrome Corporation*). The equivalent

BET particle diameter was calculated assuming the powder particles were spherical or cubic in shape [47]. Scanning electron microscope images were recorded with a *Philips XL30* ESEM (Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Powder characterization

Fig. 1 shows the IR spectrum of the orange (BaCe)-precursor **1**. A broad band around 3600–3000 cm^{-1} reveals OH stretching vibrations. Vibration maxima at 1601, 1310 and 1059 cm^{-1} represent HOH bending modes as well as the presence of oxalate anions [48,49,50]. The band at 837 cm^{-1} can be assigned to a peroxo group [48,51,52,53,54]. Additionally, bands at 771 and 526 cm^{-1} can be observed.

TG and DTA investigations in flowing air and argon atmosphere are shown in Fig. 2. In flowing air (Fig. 2a) we observed a weight loss of 14.7 % up to 600 °C, which is accompanied by two exothermic signals between 90–350 °C and 420–530 °C. This level is stable until 730 °C and consists of orthorhombic BaCO_3 and CeO_2 [60] (see also Fig. 3). A following two-step weight loss up to 1070 °C leads to the formation of BaCeO_3 . During this process an endothermic peak with an onset temperature of 810 °C can be observed. This endothermic signal is mainly caused by the phase transition from orthorhombic to hexagonal BaCO_3 and its following decomposition [55,56,57,58,59]. The total weight loss is 23.3 %. TG/DTA measurements in air with a heating rate of 1 K/min shows that up to 970 °C the (BaCe)-precursor is completely transformed into BaCeO_3 . Thermoanalytic measurements in argon atmosphere reveal a very similar decomposition behaviour (Fig. 2b). The on- and offset temperatures of the DTA peaks do not significantly differ from air measurement. The decomposition is finished at 1080 °C and exhibits a total weight loss of 23.7 %. XRD investigations of the final white product indicate orthorhombic BaCeO_3 .

Phase evolution during the thermal decomposition of the amorphous (BaCe)-precursor **1** is shown in Fig. 3. The samples were heated in a muffle furnace in static air (rate 10 K/min). Calcination at 400 °C for 1 h results in a yellow X-ray amorphous powder (Fig. 3b). It can be seen in Fig. 3a and 3b the diffractograms show very weak peaks indicating a small crystalline amount into the powders. However, those weak peaks could not be assigned. Reflections of orthorhombic BaCO₃ and cubic CeO₂ [60] appear after heating at 600 °C (Fig. 3c). Heat treatment at 800 °C leads to a light-yellow powder consisting of BaCO₃, CeO₂ and BaCeO₃ [60] (Fig. 3d). At 900 °C the amount of BaCeO₃ increases and the colour of the resulting powder turns to white. The XRD pattern after calcination at 1000 °C reveals only reflections of orthorhombic BaCeO₃ (Fig. 3e).

3.2. Sintering behaviour and characterization of ceramic bodies

As seen in Fig. 2a the final temperature for the formation of BaCeO₃ depends on the heating rate. For the following investigations, therefore, the (BaCe)-precursor **1** was calcined by the following thermal treatment in static air: heating to 600 °C with a heating rate of 10 K/min, slow heating with 1 K/min to 980 °C, and subsequently cooling with 5 K/min to room temperature. The resulting white BaCeO₃ powder (**1A**) has a specific surface area of $S = 5.8 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and an equivalent particle size of 163 nm which can be considered as an average size of the primary particles [61]. As seen in Fig. 3f powder **1A** consists of a BaCeO₃ perovskite phase and a very small amounts of BaCO₃ and CeO₂. The coarse-grained powder **3** resulting from a mixed-oxide process after calcinations at 1150 °C for 4 h has a specific surface area of $2.1 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and an equivalent particle size of 449 nm. To improve the sintering behaviour we additionally substituted 5 mol% of (NH₄)₂Ce(NO₃)₆ by Ge(OC₂H₅)₄ during the co-precipitation synthesis and obtained an amorphous (BaCe_{0.95}/Ge_{0.05})-precursor (**2**). Precursor **2** was calcined by the same thermal treatment as described for precursor **1** resulting in a white powder (**2A**).

Fig. 4 shows the non-isothermal dilatometric investigations up to 1500 °C. Samples **1A** and **2A** begin to shrink at about 1010–1020 °C. Sample **1A** shows a defined shrinkage rate maximum at 1197 °C (rate: -0.5 %/min) and a second broad maximum with a rate of -0.35 %/min at 1329 °C. In contrast, sample **2A** shows a very broad change of the shrinkage rate. Maxima appear at 1204 °C (rate: -0.36 %/min) and about 1386 °C (rate: -0.63 %/min). The shrinkage of sample **3** starts at the significantly higher temperature of about 1230 °C and shows two maxima of the shrinkage rate at 1383 °C (rate: -0.22 %/min) and at 1456 °C (rate: -0.33 %/min), respectively. The shrinkage rates of all samples indicate that the densification is dominated by sliding processes. Diffusion as the dominant process causes only shrinkage rates of about 10^{-4} to 10^{-1} %/min [33,62,63].

The evolution of the bulk densities of ceramic bodies of **1A**, **2A** and **3** after isothermal sintering with a soaking time of 1 h and 10 h is represented in Fig. 5. The bulk densities of the ceramic bodies were calculated from their weight and geometric dimensions. The relative densities of sample **1A** and **3** are related to the theoretical density (single crystal density) of 6.36 g/cm³ [64] and the densities of sample **2A** are related to 6.29 g/cm³ [65]. It can be seen that the relative densities of ceramic bodies of **3** remain always considerably below 80%. Ceramics from the co-precipitation method (**1A**) exhibit a relative density of 85% and grain sizes between about 2–12 μm after sintering for 10 h at 1500 °C (Fig. 5b, 6a). The addition of Ge⁴⁺ during the co-precipitation synthesis considerably improves the sintering behaviour of the resulting preceramic powder (**2A**). We obtained dense ceramic bodies (rel. density ≥ 90%) after 1 h at 1500 °C and even at 1350 °C after 10 h sintering (Fig. 5a,b). After a soaking time of 10 h the microstructure shows grain sizes between 0.9–3.2 μm (1350 °C, Fig. 6b), 1–5 μm (1400 °C), 1.5–6.5 μm (1450 °C, Fig. 6c), and 2.5–12 μm (1500 °C, Fig. 6d). Sintering of **2A** at 1300 °C for 50 h results in ceramics with a relative density of 88% and grain sizes between about 0.8–2.2 μm (Fig. 6e). DTA investigations up to 1460 °C of sample **2A** do not show the

formation of a liquid phase. Heat treatment below 1500 °C, therefore, is characterized by solid-state sintering. Hence, the addition of Ge⁴⁺ during the synthesis improves the densification process by supporting sliding processes [63,66,67,68].

XRD patterns of ceramic bodies of **1A**, **2A** and **3** after sintering at 1400 °C for 1 h are shown in Fig. 7. Ceramics of **1A** and **3** show only reflections of orthorhombic BaCeO₃ [60] (Fig. 7a,b). XRD data of ceramic bodies (corrected by an internal standard) were indexed on the basis of a primitive orthorhombic unit cell (Pmnc) according to Knight et al. [64,19,20]. The cell parameters were determined by least-square refinements. For BaCeO₃ ceramic bodies of **1A** lattice parameters of $a = 877.56(14)$ pm, $b = 623.66(8)$ pm, $c = 621.52(14)$ pm, $V = 340.15(8)$ pm³ were calculated. These parameters agree very well with earlier data for pure BaCeO₃ [64,19,20]. XRD investigations of ceramics of **2A** (Fig. 7c) show the pattern of orthorhombic BaCeO₃. Closer inspections in the range $2\theta = 33\text{--}39^\circ$ reveal reflections belonging to an orthorhombic Ba₂GeO₄ phase [60]. The appearance of Ba₂GeO₄ indicates the presence of CeO₂. In Fig. 7c a weak reflection at $2\theta = 38.6^\circ$ appeared representing the (200) reflection of cubic CeO₂. Lattice constants and therefore the unit cell volume of the BaCeO₃ phase of ceramics of **2A** do not significantly differ from the data of ceramics of **1A**. From this finding it can be concluded, that the addition of Ge⁴⁺ during the synthesis and the following calcinations and sintering procedure does not lead to an incorporation of Ge⁴⁺ into the BaCeO₃ lattice.

DTA data of ceramics of **1A**, **2A** and **3** are presented in Fig. 8. All samples show reversible endothermic effects between 250–280 °C, 370–400 °C (Fig. 8b), and a very weak one between 890–910 °C (Fig. 8c), representing three phase transitions, as mentioned above. The onset temperatures of the first two peaks could be determined. Sample **3** reveals onset temperatures at 260 °C and 387 °C. The onset temperatures of samples **1A** and **2A** are slightly shifted to lower temperatures of 255 °C and 383 °C (**1A**) as well as 256 °C and 380 °C (**2A**).

The observed phase transition temperatures agree very well with earlier DSC and high temperature neutron diffraction studies [19,69,70].

Conclusion

Fine-grained BaCeO₃ powders can be prepared by a co-precipitation method using a Ce⁴⁺ salt. The temperature for the formation of BaCeO₃ depends on the heating rate, and is 970 °C with a heating rate of 1 K/min. A rate controlled calcination procedure of the X-ray amorphous (BaCe)-precursor powder (**1**) leads to a BaCeO₃ powder (**1A**) with a specific surface area of 5.8 m²/g. BaCeO₃ powder (**3**) prepared by a mixed-oxide method has a specific surface area of 2.1 m²/g and shows an insufficient sintering behaviour. On the other hand sintering of compacts of **1A** to 1500 °C for 10 h leads to a bulk density of 85%. The sintering behaviour can be considerably improved using a sintering aid. During the co-precipitation synthesis 5 mol% of the Ce⁴⁺ salt were substituted by Ge⁴⁺-alkoxide forming a (BaCe_{0.95}/Ge_{0.05})-precursor (**2**). Powder compacts of the resulting calcined powder **2A**, containing a Ba–Ge–O phase, reach a relative density of 90 % with grain-sizes between 0.9–3.2 μm after sintering at 1350 °C and a soaking time of 10 h. The Ba–Ge–O phase improves the densification process by supporting sliding processes and do not act as a liquid phase former. The final ceramics of **1A** and **3** consist of phase-pure orthorhombic BaCeO₃. XRD patterns of ceramics of **2A** shows small reflections of Ba₂GeO₄ and CeO₂ besides the reflections of BaCeO₃. DTA measurements up to 1000 °C of ceramics of **1A**, **2A** and **3** reveal three reversible phase transitions.

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Fig. 1 IR spectrum of precursor 1

Fig. 2 TG and DTA curves of precursor 1 in different atmospheres. **a** Flowing air (DTA traces for a heating rate of 1 K/min not shown), **b** argon. Every 100th data point in the DTA curve is marked by a *symbol*

Fig. 3 XRD patterns (recorded at 25 °C) of precursor powder **1** (a) and decomposition products (b–e) of **1** at various temperatures (soaking time 1 h, rate 10 K/min): b 400 °C, c 600 °C, d 800 °C, e 1000 °C. f Powder 1A from a heating rate controlled calcination process at 980 °C

Fig. 4 Non-isothermal dilatometric measurements in flowing air of green bodies of 1A, 2A and 3 (heating rate 10 K/min). The *inset* shows the relative shrinkage rates ($d(\Delta L/L_0)/dt$). Every 100th data point is marked by a *symbol*

Fig. 5 Evolution of the final densities of ceramic bodies of 1A, 2A and 3 after an isothermal sintering process of a 1 h and b 10 h (rate 10 K/min)

Fig. 6 SEM images of the surface of ceramic bodies after various sintering treatments (heating rate 10 K/min). Ceramic 1A: a 1500 °C, 10 h. Ceramic 2A: b 1350 °C, 10 h; c 1450 °C, 10 h; d 1500 °C, 10 h; e 1300 °C, 50 h

Fig. 7 XRD patterns (recorded at 25 °C) of ceramic bodies sintered at 1400 °C for 1 h. a Ceramic 3, b ceramic 1A, c ceramic 2A

Fig. 8 DTA traces in flowing air of ceramic bodies of 1A, 2A and 3 sintered at 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h. Heating rate 10 K/min. **a** The whole DTA curves of ceramic 1A and 3 (ceramic 2A is not shown for clarity). **b** DTA curves of 1A, 2A and 3 between 240 and 420 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. **c** DTA curves of 1A, 2A and 3 around 900 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Every 500th (a) and 100th (b, c) data point is marked by a *symbol*

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